

Micro-chemical analysis of anthropogenic spherules and its role in spherule type discrimination[†]

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Abstract : Spherules of anthropogenic, biogenic, geogenic and cosmogenic origins are difficult to distinguish based on their size, shape, surface features despite their importance to elucidate large scale geological events such as mass extinction, palaeoclimate change, and meteoritic impacts etc. Rapid industrialization and vehicular emissions have added several other types of spherules. However, chemical analysis of different types of spherules, especially major element chemistry, has been found useful to differentiate spherules of diverse origins.

Keywords : Spherules, fly ash, anthropogenic, microtektites, impact spherules.

Introduction

Spherules having multitude of shapes, sizes, surface features and compositions originate from diverse sources (anthropogenic, terrestrial and cosmogenic) in nature and are extremely important in the interpretation of Earth and planetary processes. The spherule horizons deposited under sub-aerial and sub-aqueous conditions have helped in unravelling the paleoclimatic-conditions. Spherule layers provide lone testimony to the existence of possible terrestrial impact cratering phenomenon in the rocks of Archean age. Though their presence is not impact diagnostic but when supported by the chromium isotope, anomalous iridium values and platinum group element data, the spherules and spherule layers provide unequivocal evidence pertaining to their impact origin¹⁻⁴. Tektites and microtektites are impact ejectas and are one of the spherule types. Biogenic processes, forest wildfires and/or lightning can also lead to the formation of spherules. Silica-rich and metallic spherules are well known from coal-fired fly ash samples formed due to natural and an-

thropogenic activities. Pb-, Cr- and Pt-bearing spherules are known from vehicular sources. In nutshell, the study of spherules is interdisciplinary comprising geochemistry, geoenvironmental science, sedimentology, regional and global stratigraphy, and shock metamorphism.

This paper discusses the role of major element chemistry in deciphering the spherules of diverse origins, mainly based on Electron Microprobe data of anthropogenic spherules generated during the present study.

Identity crisis in spherule types :

It is extremely difficult to differentiate spherule types based on shape (spherical, elliptical, oval, dumbbell, tear drop), size (< 1 to 1.7 mm) and surface features (smooth to pitted surface), since anthropogenic, impact, meteorite ablation, volcanogenic and cosmic spherules may be having identical morphologies and features⁵⁻⁹ (Fig. 1). In some cases, impact craters have been identified solely based on the reported presence of spherules of uncertain origin⁵.

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Spherule type	Shape (splash form)	Surface (impact pits)	Petrography (Vesicles)	Composition	
				Linear comp. trend	H ₂ O Cont
Microtektite	Yes 	Yes			
Impact spherule	Yes (Bunch et al., 2012) 	Yes			
Anthropogenic (Silica-rich)	Yes 	Yes			

Fig. 1. Characteristic variation in spherule types (microtektites, impact spherule and anthropogenic spherules (present study)) based on shape, surface texture, petrography and chemical composition.

Results

The chemistry of 10 spherules from the present study and published data of impact spherules and microtektites are given in Table 1. The anthropogenic spherules in the present study are spherical, elliptical, oval, dumbbell,

cylindrical, tear-drop and spindle shaped, having dominance of spherical ones with 84%. The surface texture deals with the hypervelocity impact pits which can be seen in both microtektites and impact spherules whereas rare in anthropogenic spherules. In petrography, vesicles

Table 1. Major oxide analyses of 10 representative spherules comprising microtektites, impact spherules and anthropogenic (present study) presented here for comparison along with their size, shape and colour

Spherule type	Shape	Size	Colour	Chemical composition (Wt. %)
Microtektites	Spherical, elongated, tear-drop, discs or dumbbell and spindle	< 1 mm	Honey coloured, light yellow, yellowish green to opaque white	SiO ₂ : 56.26–75.74 (Avg. 68.59) Na ₂ O : 0.41–1.04 (Avg. 0.66) K ₂ O : 0.33–2.02 (Avg. 1.00) Al ₂ O ₃ : 10.63–21.12 (Avg. 15.33) MgO : 2.38–10.62 (Avg. 4.66) CaO : 2.06–4.14 (Avg. 3.24) FeO ^T : 3.97–9.16 (Avg. 5.42) TiO ₂ : 0.56–1.07 (Avg. 0.84)
Impact spherule	Spherical, tear-drop, cylinder, dumbbell and spindle	≈ 0.3 to 1 mm	Light to dark grey (depends upon target lithology)	SiO ₂ : 43.33–51.39 (Avg. 48.31) Al ₂ O ₃ : 11.76–15.23 (Avg. 13.67) Na ₂ O : 1.23–2.38 (Avg. 1.81) MgO : 4.95–8.93 (Avg. 6.84) K ₂ O : 0.19–0.78 (Avg. 0.32) CaO : 8.21–10.71 (Avg. 9.24) FeO ^T : 11.96–16.89 (Avg. 15.27) TiO ₂ : 1.94–2.95 (Avg. 2.32) P ₂ O ₅ : 0.02–0.16 (Avg. 0.07)
Anthropogenic spherule (present study)	Spherical, oval, dumbbell, spindle and tear-drop	0.4–1.7 mm	Colourless to dark grey, opaque white and brown	SiO ₂ : 67.96–85.59 (Avg. 72.09) Al ₂ O ₃ : 1.21–3.63 (Avg. 1.70) Na ₂ O : 0.19–6.79 (Avg. 2.31) MgO : 3.62–0.30 (Avg. 1.97) K ₂ O : 0.26–1.04 (Avg. 0.50) CaO : 5.01–10.16 (Avg. 7.57) TiO ₂ : 0.01–0.08 (Avg. 0.03) FeO ^T : 0.07–0.40 (Avg. 0.21) P ₂ O ₅ : 0.09–0.17 (Avg. 0.13)

and microlites have been observed in all types of spherules; however they differ in spatially spread. The SiO₂ content ranges between 67.96 and 85.59 wt.% with an average value of 72.09 wt.%, Na₂O (0.19–6.79 wt.%), Al₂O₃ (1.21 and 3.63 wt.%) and K₂O (0.26–1.04 wt.%) values. Total iron content is expressed as FeO which is low (0.07–0.40 wt.%). The distinction can be made on the basis of lithophile (present study)/siderophile elemental concentration. The average SiO₂ content in microtektite and impact spherule is 68.59 and 48.31 wt.%, respectively^{10,11}. The Na₂O concentration in microtektite ranges from 0.41 to 1.04 wt.% and impact spherule contains between 1.23 and 2.38 wt.% (Figs. 2a, b) which is much less than those of anthropogenic (fly ash) origin.

The source of silica-rich spherules is from a coal-fired thermal power plant, Phulpur. The metallic spherules

on the other hand are the by-products of the industries and/or vehicular emissions. The linear composition is showing linear trend in case of microtektite and impact spherule but no such trend has been observed in spherules of anthropogenic origin. Water content is also observed in all types of spherule where microtektite bears less water content but anthropogenic silica-rich spherule are hygroscopic in nature and has high water content.

Discussions

Thus it can be conclude from the above study that the spherical shape is neither an indicator of impact process nor of melting. The size, shape (spherical, ovoid, dumbbell, tear-drop and cylindrical) and surface features (pits and craters) of anthropogenic (fly-ash, vehicular combustion and industrial emanations) spherules are similar to

Fig. 2. (a) Binary Al₂O₃ vs SiO₂ plot showing distinct domains of anthropogenic spherule (open circle; present study) from Allahabad RDS, microtektites (shaded circle) from Indian ocean¹⁰, and spherules from Lonar impact structure, Maharashtra, India (solid circle)¹¹. (b) Ternary SiO₂-(CaO + MgO + FeO^T)-Al₂O₃ diagram showing distinct clusters among the three spherule types. FeO^T represents total iron expressed as FeO¹².

those formed due to volcanism, impact cratering (including tektites and microtektites) and cosmic events. BSE-SEM images shows resembling morphology between anthropogenic spherules, microtektites and impact spherule and it is nearly impossible to differentiate the anthropogenic spherules from the spherules of cosmogenic/impact origins. The major oxide chemistry of anthropogenic spherules can be selectively used to distinguish other spherule types. The data on anthropogenic spherules worldwide is nearly non-existent. The size of fly-ash generated

anthropogenic spherules (0.1–1000 μm) with more than 77 thermal power plants in India and spatial spread of over hundreds of km of the particulate matter in each thermal power plant, which is needed to be kept in vigil.

Experimental

The spherules were separated under a stereo zoom microscope from the road-deposited sediments of Allahabad city after sieving (both sieved and un-sieved portion) were taken (35 mesh) and consequently mounted

on a glass slide¹². The surface features of the spherules were studied with the help of a binocular zoom microscope. The sub-microscopic study and micro-chemical analysis were carried out in Physical Research Laboratory, Ahmedabad with the help of an Electron Probe Micro Analyzer (EPMA; Cameca SX-100). The spherules were mounted with Araldite® on a conducting metallic stub of 2.5 cm diameter and coated with either gold or carbon. The accelerating voltage of 10–15 kV, 25 mA beam current and 1–10 µm beam diameter were used for the analyses. Both natural and synthetic standards were used for calibration. The detection limit was between 0.1 and 0.5 weight% depending on the element. SEM and BSE (Backscattered Electron) images were acquired to observe surface texture and chemical variability, respectively.

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